

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

FRZB (Frizzled Related Protein)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	2487 / Q92765
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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Protein constructs & expression methods: Full-length Human FRZB (E33-E325) without signal peptide

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1 (1,2).

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.22 (rank #3571, 85.7th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.22 out of 5 (rank #3571, 85.7th percentile). The individual score components include 1.26 of 3 for genetics, and 1.97 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of FRZB, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. FRZB is annotated to GO terms from the Apoptosis domain.

Overall	rank	pct	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.224	3571	85.7	1.259	1.965

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of FRZB is not confidently detected in any cells within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

FRZB is a negative regulator of Wnt signalling with anti-oncogenic properties observed within some cancer types. The link to AD, as noted below, is three-fold: (1) as a regulator of Wnt signalling (2,3), (2) as an inhibitor of ADAM17 mediated proteolysis(4), and (3) due to its involvement in module 42 (M42), a module identified in deep proteomic investigation of AD case-controls, which is strongly associated with both cognition and pathological progression (5). The basic target enablement package (TEP) developed here will provide validated antibodies, purified protein, and a bioinformatics workup of the FRZB gene. The deployment of novel useful resources for the scientific community will hopefully advance investigations within the academic and pharmaceutical industries to better understand the role played by FRZB in AD, and its potential as a novel target against disease progression.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The Frizzled Related Protein (FRZB) is a secreted protein of 313 amino acids (approximately 34 KD) with two functional domains: an N-terminal Cysteine Rich Domain (CRD) and a C-terminal NTR domains shared across the frizzled protein family (2,6). The N-terminal CRD enables FRZB to bind to Wnt family members (7,8). FRZB binds to Wnt ligands and inhibits their activity, which is the putative mechanism through which FRZB modulates tissue development in numerous anatomical regions including muscle (9–11), palate (12,13), auditory sensory cells (14) and FRZB is present in early neural tube formation (15–17), suggesting a potential role in early neural developmental processes. FRZB is also linked to bone formation and osteoblast formation and as genetic variants in FRZB can trigger the osteoporosis (10,18,19). Diseases of muscle formation, namely limb girdle muscular dystrophy type 2 (8,20,21), show altered levels of FRZB, but it is not clear whether this is linked to the causal disease pathogenesis. The C-terminal NTR domain bears resemblance to metalloproteinase inhibitory proteins (22), potentially linking FRZB to neural endoproteolytic events (3,17). Additionally, FRZB associates with heparin proteoglycans (19,23), a class of protein observed to be altered in AD pathogenesis.

The link between FRZB and AD is unclear, but it was identified in deep proteomic evaluation of AD brain tissue in case control post-mortem studies as being up-regulated within core modules associated with AD cognitive function and pathology (2). Interestingly, FRZB is also associated with regulating numerous forms of cancer, likely through regulation of Wnt cellular propagation signalling. There is a long-standing observation of connections between oncology and AD (24–26), and cell cycle dysregulation has been proposed as a contributor to neurodegeneration in AD progression (27). The NTR domain is similar to metalloproteinase inhibitors that regulate proteins such as the ADAM family (22), which is involved in non-pathogenic APP processing, and FRZB inhibits ADAM17, one of the canonical alpha-secretases mediating non-amyloidogenic APP proteolysis (3). Wnt signalling may play a role in AD pathology, with numerous family members dysregulated in the disease state (28). How the interaction between FRZB and Wnt may be involved in AD pathology, if at all, is unknown, but FRZB binding to Wnt ligands also increases their range of diffusion within biological systems, potentially promoting either a clearance or an enhanced range of Wnt ligands (29). The development of resources to rigorously test the role of FRZB disease process may illuminate its biological role in modulating Wnt signalling and ADAM-mediated proteolysis AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. FRZBA-c400: Full-length Human FRZB (E33-E325) without signal peptide. Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of FRZB in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

Additional Information

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. FRZBA-c400: Full-length Human FRZB (E33-E325) without signal peptide. Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	FRZBA-c400
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	39227.9 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	40910
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGAACEPVRIPLCKSLPWNMTKMPNHLHHSTQ ANAILAIEQFEGLLGTHCSPDLLFFLCAMYAPICTIDFQHEPIKPKSVGERARQGCEPILIKYR HSWPENLACEELPVYDRGVCISPEAIVTADGADFPMDSSNGNCRGASSERCKCKPIRATQK TYFRNNYNYVIRAKVKEIKTKCHDVTAVVEVKEILKSSLVNI PRDVTNLYTSSGCLCPPLNVNE EYIIMGYEDEERSRLLLVEGSIAEKWKDRLGKKVWRWDMKLRHLGLSKSDSSNSDSTQSQKS GRNSNPRQARNGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

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Purified Protein	
Heparin affinity chromatography: FRZBA-c400 (with tag)	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Heparin Purification</i></p>
Intact Mass Deconvolution: SFRP1-c500 (with tag)	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	0.7 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian:</i> Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol.

For more information or questions regarding the TEP, please contact treatad.info@sagebionetworks.org

	Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1×10^6 cells/ml in 200 ml FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2×10^6 cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Heparin W1 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 2% glycerol 5. Heparin W2 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 2% glycerol 6. Heparin elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 1.5 M NaCl, 1% glycerol 7. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer. 8. Hi-Trap Heparin HP Column (Cytiva), equilibrated in Heparin W1 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Heparin affinity chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Apply EB fractions containing the protein, using a syringe 'drop to drop' onto the column. 2. Wash the column with 10 ml of W1, followed by 10 ml of W2. 3. Elute protein with 3x 2ml heparin elution buffer. 4. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using UV spectroscopy. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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